

Dissociation Constants of Thiolactic Acid

R. S. Saxena and Pratap Singh

The acid dissociation constants of thiolactic acid have been determined potentiometrically and polarographically at three different temperatures. pK_{D_1} values have been found to be 3.63, 3.66 and 3.70 and pK_{D_2} values as 10.24, 10.18 and 10.11 at 20°, 30° and 40° respectively. (pK_{D_1} and pK_{D_2} terms represent the negative logarithms of the dissociation constants of -COOH and -SH groups). The heat of ionization for the first dissociation constant was calculated as -4.75 K.cal/mole.

Thiolactic acid, containing -COOH and -SH groups, belonging to a physiologically important class of compounds called mercaptans, has gained sufficient importance in the fields of pharmaceutical¹⁻⁵, synthetic⁶ and analytical⁷ chemistry in recent years. The polarographic behaviour of this compound has already been studied by the authors⁸ but there is hardly any reference in the literature reporting its dissociation constants.

A knowledge of the acid dissociation constants of simple mercaptans is fundamental to an understanding of the chemistry of these compounds for two reasons; firstly because many important reactions of mercaptans may proceed through the mercaptide ions, and secondly, the acid dissociation constants can give important information about the distribution of electrons in mercaptans. Moreover, these values are essential for investigating the complexing tendency of such compounds with metals.

In view of its importance and in the absence of any literature on the subject, it was considered worthwhile to determine the acid dissociation constants of -COOH and -SH groups in thiolactic acid at different temperatures *viz.*, 20°, 30° and 40° using potentiometric and polarographic techniques.

EXPERIMENTAL

Thiolactic acid was supplied by Evan's Chemetics, Inc. N.Y. assaying 98%. All other chemicals were either reagent grade or Merck's guaranteed extra pure quality and

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2. Henry, A. Schroeder, Edna M. Menhard and Mitchell H. Perry (Jr.), *J. Lab. Clin. Med.*, 1955, **45**, 431.
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their solutions were prepared in doubly distilled air-free conductivity water. Freshly prepared solutions were always used to avoid the effects of ageing and air oxidation.

Polarographic measurements were performed with a Cambridge (G.P.) polarograph equipped with thermostated H-cell and saturated calomel electrode. The capillary had the following characteristics measured in 0.1 *M* NaClO₄; $m = 1.563$ mg/sec, $t = 3.21$ secs (Vs. S.C.E.). Doubly distilled mercury was used for the dropping mercury electrode.

A Cambridge bench pattern (null deflection type) *pH* meter was used for *pH* measurements. A wide range glass electrode, calibrated frequently by using buffer solution of different *pH* values, was used in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode connected to the cell by a low resistance salt bridge. Calibration was made before and after each series of measurements. All the *pH* titrations were carried out in aqueous medium. The temperatures were controlled by an electrically maintained thermostat (Universal Thermostat type U3),

Polarographic study: For each polarographic measurement, the solution to be polarographed was prepared in 25 ml of a volumetric flask by the addition of a known volume of the standard solutions so as to give the required concentration of the various contents in 25 ml. Thoroughly mixed solution was then transferred to the cell from which dissolved air was removed by bubbling oxygen free nitrogen and a complete inert atmosphere was maintained over the solution during electrolysis. Polarograms were then recorded and half-wave potentials were determined by the conventional logarithmic plots.

Potentiometric study: A known volume of the standard thiolactic acid solution was taken so as to give 0.01 *M* thiolactic acid in 30 ml. Ionic strength ($\mu = 0.1$ *M*) was maintained by adding requisite amount of *M* NaClO₄. The solution was then titrated with CO₂ free 0.1 *N* NaOH solution using a Cambridge *pH* meter, equipped with a glass electrode, in nitrogen atmosphere and a titration curve was drawn from which the dissociation constants were calculated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thiolactic acid has two replaceable hydrogen ions as indicated in the formula below :

The equilibria involved are

where H₂A represents the thiolactic acid and parentheses denote molar concentrations. The acid dissociation constants K_{D₁} and K_{D₂}, which correspond to the carboxylic hydrogen

atom and to the hydrogen atom linked to the sulphur atom respectively, are determined potentiometrically and polarographically.

Potentiometric determination of dissociation constants : The titration curve of thiolactic acid with sodium hydroxide indicates two buffer regions—one between *pH* 2.86 to 4.9 and the other beyond *pH* 9.5. A strong inflection in the vicinity of *pH* 7.0 corresponds to the formation of sodium salt of the thiolactic acid. Thus, the first buffer region is attributed to the carboxylic acid group. K_{D_1} is evaluated from the first buffer region by employing method of Albert and Serjeant⁹. K_{D_2} is calculated from the second buffer region, *i.e.*, from the part of the neutralization curve pertaining to the species $[HA^-]$, in the usual manner.

The values of the dissociation constants obtained at different temperatures are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Dissociation Constants of Thiolactic acid at different temperatures

Temperature °C	Potentiometric study		Polarographic study
	pK_{D_1}	pK_{D_2}	pK_{D_2}
20	3.63	10.24	10.26
30	3.66	10.18	10.19
40	3.70	10.11	10.00

It is noted that ionization constants vary with temperature, the values of K_{D_1} are found to increase with rise in temperature whereas K_{D_2} shows a gradual decrease within temperature range studied. The plot of $\log K_{D_1}$ against $1/T$ had been found to be linear which yields the heat of ionization for the first dissociation step as -4.75 K cal/mole.

Polarographic determination of dissociation constants of sulphhydryl group : The determination of K_{D_2} is carried out polarographically at follows :—

Polarograms of 1.0 mM thiolactic acid in Clark and Lubs buffer solutions of different *pH* values were recorded at temperatures 20°, 30° and 40° (*e.g.*, Fig. 1 at 30°). Thiolactic acid produces an anodic wave at all *pH* values (5.64–12.0) and the total current was found to be diffusion controlled and corresponds to one electron change in all the polarograms.

The characteristics of the anodic wave of thiolactic acid have already been established by us⁸. It has been shown that the anodic wave is due to the formation of a mercury compound as indicated below :

(RSH refers to thiolactic acid)

9. A. Albert and E. P. Serjeant, "Ionization constants of acids and bases", Methuen and Co. Ltd., (London), pp. 16–34.

The potential at any point on the wave occurring as a result of this reaction is given by

$$E_{d.e.} = E_{\frac{1}{2}} - 0.059 \log \frac{i d^{-i}}{i} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. Polarograms of 1.0 mM Thiolactic acid at different pH values at 30°.

The Nernst equation of the anodic wave corresponding to the reaction (1), may be written as

$$E_{d.e.} = E^{\circ} + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{[\text{RSHg}]^{\circ} [\text{H}^+]^{\circ}}{[\text{RSH}]^{\circ}} \quad (3)$$

where E° is the standard potential. Considering that the sulphhydryl group in RSH is a weak acid with an ionization constant K_{D_2} , the potential in buffered solution may be written as

$$E_{d.e.} = E^{\circ} + 0.059 \log k/k_1 + 0.059 \log \{[\text{H}^+] + K_{D_2}\} - 0.059 \log \frac{i d^{-i}}{i} \quad (4)$$

where k and k_1 are constants which are proportional to the square roots of the diffusion coefficient of thiolactic acid and its mercury compound [RSHg] respectively.

Combining equation (2) and (4) the half wave potential is expressed by

$$E_{\frac{1}{2}} = E^1 + 0.059 \log \{[\text{H}^+] + K_{D_2}\} \quad (5)$$

where the constant E^1 is equal to $E^{\circ} + 0.059 \log k/k_1$.

Fig. 2 shows plots of pH vs. half wave potentials of anodic waves of 1.0 mM RSH at 20°, 30° and 40°. It is seen that there are two linear portions in the plots whose intersection correspond to the pH = 10.26, 10.19 and 10.0 at 20°, 30° and 40° respectively. This indicates that under the conditions of the experiments, the H^+ ion of the sulphhydryl group has $pK_{D_2} = 10.26, 10.19$ and 10.0 at 20°, 30 and 40° respectively¹⁰.

10. M. Brezina and P. Zuman, "Polarography in medicine, biochemistry and pharmacy, Interscience Publishers Inc., N.Y., 1958, 470-473.

The values of pK_{D_2} obtained from polarographic method are in close agreement with those calculated from potentiometric titration technique.

FIG 2

Fig. 2. Plots of E_{v_2} as a function of pH at 20° , 30° and 40° .

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Department of Chemistry,
Malaviya Regional Engineering College,
Jaipur.

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